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PROBLEMS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: WORLD EXPERIENCE
AND FEATURES OF ENTERPRISES OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

Abstract: *Digital transformation is an important factor influencing the competitiveness and sustainable development of enterprises on a global scale. The article examines the key problems that arise in the course of digital transformation of enterprises and analyzes the international experience of successful implementation of digital technologies. Major obstacles, such as limited financial resources, a shortage of qualified professionals and inadequate infrastructure. The article offers recommendations for overcoming these barriers and accelerating the digital transformation process in Moldova, including the development of educational programs, state support for digitalization and infrastructure improvement.*

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In today's era of rapid technological progress, called Industrialization 4.0, digital transformation is becoming an integral element of the strategic development of companies. The introduction of digital technologies and the transition to new platforms allow enterprises to increase their competitiveness, improve the quality of services and products provided, as well as optimize internal processes, improve relationships between all beneficiaries, develop creativity and gain competitive advantages through all this. At the global level, many companies have already undergone or are in the process of digital transformation, facing a variety of challenges and obstacles. However, it is worth noting that digital transformation is by no means a fashionable term, or a panacea for all ills. Its implementation encounters many problems and obstacles, both among the subjective moments related to the staff and their attitude and understanding of all processes, and from the point of view of objective problems related to resources, technologies, legislation, etc.

The Republic of Moldova, seeking to integrate digital technologies into the economy and business, also faces unique challenges that require special attention and adapted solutions. Exploring these challenges and developing effective strategies to overcome them are becoming key challenges to ensure a successful digital transformation in a country.

The purpose of this article is to study the problems of digital transformation on the example of Moldovan enterprises, to analyze the world experience in the

implementation of digital technologies and to offer recommendations for the successful integration of digital innovations. The article examines both general and specific barriers for Moldova, as well as proposes ways to overcome them based on the best world practices.

Digital transformation is the process of integrating digital technologies into all aspects of business, which leads to fundamental changes in the way companies operate and deliver value to customers. In this process, every aspect of the business is transformed: the business model is revised, business processes are transformed, and often the way organizations operate. According to George Westerman of the MIT Sloan School of Management, "Digital transformation is not just about technology, but about how technology can change your business model and create new revenue streams" (Westerman, 2024).

"Successful transformation is not a one-time action, but an ongoing process that requires flexibility of thinking and creating an organizational structure that will allow the company to constantly respond to constantly emerging digital trends" (Jeanne Ross, Ina Sebastian, Cynthia Beet, 2018). This quote quite clearly defines the need to reorient business to acquire a new consciousness, capable of updating as necessary, and therefore always.

Global experience shows that successful digital transformation requires not only the introduction of new technologies, but also changes in organizational culture, business processes and strategies. According to a McKinsey study, companies that successfully undergo digital transformation significantly increase their productivity and profitability. At the same time, the percentage of successful transformations is less than 30% (McKinsey, 2018). According to the researchers, "transformations are complex in themselves, and even more so, digital transformations are even more complex." According to the results of the research company Bain, comparing traditional and digital transformation, in the second case, the statistics are less encouraging and optimistic if we talk about expectations (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Comparing the results of traditional and digital change

(Adapted by the author based on the results of research:

<https://www.bain.com/insights/orchestrating-a-successful-digital-transformation>)

This is followed by statistics by industry, which also makes you think about the problems and prospects of digital transformation. For example, only 16% of respondents say that digital transformation in their organizations has successfully improved operational efficiency (even though this is the true meaning of the transformation). Also, 7% of respondents say that the indicators have improved, but these improvements have not been sustainable in the long term, in our opinion, such transformations do not make sense for a short-term orientation, given the complexity, scale and cost of change programs.

Even industries such as high technology, media, and telecommunications cannot cope with this task. In these industries, the share of successful results does not exceed 26%. And in more traditional industries, such as oil and gas, automotive, infrastructure, and pharmaceuticals, digital transformation is even more difficult, with success rates ranging from 4 to 11% (McKinsey, 2018).

So, when exploring the reasons for the failure of digital transformation, let's turn to a Gartner study that identifies nine main reasons for the failure of digital transformation.

According to researchers, the failure of digital transformations occurs for the following reasons (Gartner, 2019) :

1. ***Lack of awareness of the scale of digital transformation.*** The company does not realize how radically its business model will change and how significant these changes will be, so its strategy does not assume scale in terms of finances, human and time resources;
2. ***Focus on internal structure.*** The organization focuses on internal issues, ignoring the analysis of the external environment, including customer needs, opportunities and market opportunities. At the same time, digital transformation is perceived as a normal change in the operating model.
3. ***Detachment of management.*** Often, the management believes that digitalization is not their lot, boards of directors and top managers believe that digital transformation is the task of IT specialists and do not see the need to personally participate in this process, which they are deeply mistaken about and risk of not being able to cope with such large-scale changes.
4. ***Unclear goals.*** As with any organizational change process, a digital transformation strategy must have clear and concise goals. The problem here is that the organization lacks a clear vision of what it wants to achieve through digital transformation. Targets and indicators are not defined.
5. ***Small steps instead of a radical and comprehensive transformation.*** Digital transformation is perceived as a series of small improvements, rather than a full-fledged transformation, which contradicts the very essence of digitalization as a comprehensive change project.
6. ***"Ossified" thinking, lack of desire to change.*** Employees are not ready to learn new things and resist innovation. This can be due to numerous reasons: unwillingness to leave the comfort zone, lack of motivation, lack of understanding of what exactly needs to be done, etc.
7. ***Excessive planning.*** Sometimes the planning process is counterintuitive – trying to plan in detail for all aspects of digital transformation when there is a

lack of information leads to analysis paralysis, the process can be delayed, attempts to get information can fail, or too much time will be wasted, which also slows down the effective implementation of changes.

8. ***Technological focus.*** A digitalization strategy can be reduced mainly to chasing the latest trends and technological innovations, instead of solving real business problems, without taking into account the specifics of the company's management and strategic planning.
9. ***Ignoring cultural change.*** One of the most important aspects may not be taken into account or not sufficiently thought out. When introducing changes, the cultural aspect is ignored, perceiving it as something cumbersome and difficult to change, so culture often remains outside the attention zone.

All these problems, factors, of course, intersect with the Moldovan reality and are typical for national companies. At the same time, we will highlight the features of Moldovan business, which determine the specifics of the changes.

Features of Moldovan business in characterizing the transformation process:

- ***Significant dependence on foreign markets.*** Moldovan companies in most cases depend on imports and foreign markets, which requires special attention to international digital trends and standards.
- ***Limited resources at the micro and macro levels.*** The lack of financial and human resources inherent in Moldovan companies makes it difficult to implement large-scale digital projects.
- ***Bureaucratic barriers.*** A high level of bureaucracy, largely an echo of the old system, and regulatory restrictions can slow down the digital transformation process.
- ***Low level of digital literacy of the population and the majority of employees of enterprises.*** A lack of digital knowledge and skills among employees makes it difficult to implement new solutions.
- ***Social and cultural characteristics.*** A conservative attitude towards change and distrust of new technologies can slow down the transformation process. This problem affects not only Moldovan companies, although in the territorial aspect it is very serious, given the above-mentioned restrictions.
- ***Underdeveloped infrastructure.*** Many regions of Moldova suffer from a lack of high-quality Internet infrastructure and access to modern technologies, which naturally affects transformation processes.
- ***Small business size and the resulting problems.*** Most Moldovan companies are small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which may experience difficulties in implementing digital technologies due to limited opportunities in all resources: financial, labor, lack of specialists and strategies, etc.
- ***Financial instability.*** Economic instability and currency fluctuations in the Republic of Moldova may make it difficult to invest in digital transformation.

- **Difficulties in attracting investments.** Foreign investors, in many cases, are skeptical about investments in Moldovan business, primarily because of political and economic risks.

A study conducted by the author in the period from February to May 2023, dedicated to the creation of a model of change for SMEs in the context of Industrialization 4.0, showed the following results regarding the problems of implementing changes. The chart presents the weighted average values of a sample of 210 companies that had to rate the level of resistance to change on a scale from 1 to 8. So, the diagram looks like this:

Figure 2: Ranking of problems related to the implementation of changes at the studied enterprises, arithmetic mean value of the factor (author's research results)

The chart is a ranking of the challenges that companies face in implementing digital transformation in order of their importance.

The key problems in the implementation of changes are: lack of understanding of the need for changes among the staff" and "financial difficulties". This points to the need to increase awareness and support for change among employees, as well as improve financial planning and resources. Challenges related to corporate aspects include: challenges related to corporate culture, leadership style, and organizational structure are also significant, underscoring the importance of adapting the corporate environment for successful digital transformation. Barriers related to communication and goals: Lack of clarity of goals and weak horizontal connections also hinder successful transformation, indicating the need for better communication and strategic planning.

Conclusions: as can be seen from the results of the study, the problems of Moldovan SMEs in the implementation of transformation are very similar to global trends, at the same time, they have their own nuances related to the political, economic and cultural characteristics of the country. Digital transformation is significantly more complex than traditional transformation. As it turned out, only 5% of companies meet or exceed expectations in digital transformation, which is

significantly lower than 12% in traditional transformations, although this figure is also low. 20% of companies do not achieve even half of the expected results in both traditional and digital transformation. The majority of companies (75 percent) are content with reduced value and mediocre results in digital transformation, which is higher than traditional transformations (68 percent).

The main problems of digital transformation identified by the researchers and analyzed in the framework of this work:

- Lack of understanding of the need for change among staff is the most significant problem, rated at 4.41 points, indicating the need for increased awareness and support among employees;
- Financial difficulties - the lack of financial resources to support and implement digital transformation is a significant obstacle (4.36 points), which requires improved financial planning and allocation of funds;
- Weak staff motivation - a low level of employee motivation (4.32 points) indicates the need to develop incentives and incentive programs to support change.
- Lack of desire for change on the part of management - managers are also not aware of the importance of change (4.18 points), which requires better training and informing managers;
- Company leaders need to adapt their management style to support and promote digital transformation (4.09 points), there is a need for entire leadership development programs in the context of digital transformation;
- Rigid management structures (4.03 points) hinder flexibility and adaptation, which requires organizational reforms, changes in both the organizational structure itself and the principles of interaction in the organization.
- The company's culture must support innovation and change (3.88 points), which requires changes in corporate values and norms. This issue is considered both at the international level and at the level of Moldovan enterprises, being the main factor of successful changes in the context of Industrialization 4.0.
- Lack of coordination and collaboration between departments (3.79 points) hinders successful transformation, which indicates the need to improve internal communication, as already noted in the problem with the need to change the organizational structure.
- The vagueness of goals and directions (3.73 points) indicates the need for better strategic planning, a rethinking of values, and goal setting.

The need for a comprehensive approach is the key to the success of digital transformations. Successful digital transformation requires a holistic approach that includes improving corporate culture, leadership style, organizational structure, financial planning, and employee engagement. Raising awareness and support for change among all levels of staff and management is a key success factor. Clear goals and improved coordination between departments and levels of the company are critical to the successful implementation of digital change.

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